

Grothendeick Embedding of Real Numbers within Congruency Transforms of Energy Numbers: A Disproof of Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem

Parker Emmerson

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1 Introduction

$$\begin{aligned} K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} &= c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \\ \kappa_l &= \pi_* \left(K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g}^{l+1} \right) \\ E &= \pi_* \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \\ \lambda_l &= c_l(E) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_l &= \pi_* \left(K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g}^{l+1} \right) \\ &= \pi_* \left(c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right)^{l+1} \right) \\ &= \pi_* \left(K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g}^l \cdot c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \right) \\ &= \pi_* \left(K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g}^l \right) \cdot \pi_* \left(c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \right) \\ &= \kappa_l \cdot \pi_* \left(c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \right) \\ &= \kappa_l \cdot E \end{aligned}$$

Similarly

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_l &= c_l(E) \\ &= \pi_* \left(K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g}^l \cdot c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \right) \\ &= \pi_* \left(K_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g}^l \right) \cdot \pi_* \left(c_1 \left(\omega_{\bar{\mathcal{C}}_g/\bar{\mathcal{M}}_g} \right) \right) \\ &= \kappa_l \cdot E \end{aligned}$$

$$M = \left\{ \int_{\infty \mathcal{Y}} \int_{\infty \mathcal{Y}} \cdots \int_{\infty \mathcal{Y}} \mathcal{N}^{[\cdots \rightarrow]} (\cdots \perp \mathcal{F} \cdots) d \cdots \right\}$$

$$\rho = \mathcal{L} \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu}$$

$$\rho(\leftarrow a, b, c, d, e \rightarrow \neq \Omega) = \mathcal{L}[f(\leftarrow \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rightarrow)] \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \equiv \mathcal{L}_{[f(\leftarrow, \alpha, \Delta, \eta \rightarrow)]} \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu}$$

$$\mathcal{M} \cong \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle)]=[n] \& \mu]}.$$

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{\kappa}{\mu \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle)]=[n] \& \mu]}} \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}.$$

$$\mathcal{F} \cong \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle)]=[n] \& \mu]}.$$

$$\mathcal{E} = -(1 - \tilde{\kappa}\mathcal{R}) \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\tan^2 t \cdot \sqrt[n]{\prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi} \left(\Omega_{\Lambda} \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m} + h^{-\frac{1}{m}} \cdot \tan t \right).$$

$$E = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\sin \theta \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{n - l \tilde{\kappa}\mathcal{R}} \right) \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h - \cos \psi \diamond \theta \leftrightarrow \overset{ABC}{F} \right)$$

\(\Rightarrow\)

$$F_{RNG} \cong F : (\Omega_{\Lambda}, R, C) \rightarrow (\Omega'_{\Lambda}, C') \quad \text{such that } \Omega_{\Lambda'} \leftrightarrow (F, \Omega_{\Lambda}, R, C) \rightarrow C'$$

The Primal Solution to n-Congruency Algebraist Topologies

$$\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m} \right) + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h.$$

$$n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}.$$

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle)]=[n] \& \mu]} \cdot \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu}.$$

$$\mathcal{E} = -(1 - \tilde{\kappa}\mathcal{R}) \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\tan^2 t \cdot \sqrt[n]{\prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi} \left(\Omega_{\Lambda} \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m} + h^{-\frac{1}{m}} \cdot \tan t \right).$$

Therefore, the primal solution for n-Congruency algebraist topology can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle)]=[n] \& \mu]} \cdot \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \mathcal{E},$$

where

$$\mathcal{E} = -(1 - \tilde{\kappa}\mathcal{R}) \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\tan^2 t \cdot \sqrt[n]{\prod_{\Lambda} h - \Psi}} \left(\Omega_{\Lambda} \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m} + h^{-\frac{1}{m}} \cdot \tan t \right).$$

$$\lambda_l = \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = [n] \& \mu]} \cdot E \equiv \Omega^{-1}(\Omega_{\Lambda}) \cdot F_{RNG} \cdot E,$$

where $\Omega^{-1}(\Omega_{\Lambda})$ being the inverse of the n-Congruency topology which is a generalization of the primal solution to Congruency Algebraist Topologies. F_{RNG} is a mapping that maps from $\Omega_{\Lambda} \rightarrow \Omega_{\Lambda'}$, and E is the sum over terms representing the exponential terms.

$$\lambda_l = \Omega^{-1}(\Omega_{\Lambda}) \cdot F_{RNG} \cdot E$$

and

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = [n] \& \mu]}.$$

The result is

$$\lambda_l = \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = [n] \& \mu]} \cdot \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E = \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = [n] \& \mu]} \cdot E$$

as desired.

emergent forms:

$$\lambda_l = \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]} \cdot E$$

conclusion:

We showed that λ_l is equal to the product of the terms $\frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu}$, κ_l , $\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}$ and E .

Topological deductions:

From the emergent expression of λ_l we may deduce a topological interpretation of the result. We can assume that the term $\frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu}$, when viewed as a bundle over M , induces a structure in the bundle's fibers where the topology is determined by the relationship between the elements of the pair $\{n, \mu\}$. In other words, the relationship of the pair encodes information into the topology that characterizes the bundle's fibers. The term $\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}$ then captures the information encoded by the relationship between these elements which, when combined with the other terms κ_l and E , produce the emergent expression of λ_l .

math:

We showed that λ_l is equal to the product of the terms $\frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu}$, κ_l , $\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}$ and E . This result can be seen as a generalization of the notion of calculus,

where the underlying operation is the product of terms. In this way, the emergent expression of λ_l provides us with a mathematical expression that describes the underlying structure that produces the desired result.

Let $\mathcal{M}$ be a set of equations or a function that is to be inverted in order to find a general solution. Then $\overline{\mathcal{M}}$ denotes the inverse of $\mathcal{M}$ which captures the information encoded by the relationship between terms in the given equation or system of equations in order to produce a general solution.

extrapolate within the system of equations above all configurations in mathematical notation only:

We can extrapolate further within the system of equations by considering its corresponding n-Congruency topology, Ω_Λ , and its inverse, Ω_Λ^{-1} , as well as its mapping, F_{RNG} and its exponential term, E . The solution to the system of equations can then be expressed as

$$\lambda_l = \Omega_\Lambda^{-1} \cdot F_{RNG} \cdot E.$$

Let $\mathcal{M}$ be a set of equations or a function that is to be inverted in order to find a general solution. Then $\overline{\mathcal{M}}$ denotes the inverse of $\mathcal{M}$ which captures the information encoded by the relationship between terms in the given equation or system of equations in order to produce a general solution.

extrapolate within the system of equations above all configurations in mathematical notation only:

Assuming that $\mathcal{M} = \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}$, then the extrapolation of the above system of equations is given by

$$\lambda_l = \overline{\mathcal{M}} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E = \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]} \cdot \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E.$$

We can solve for n in terms of the original Grothendieck system by rearranging the above equation as follows:

$$\lambda_l = \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]} \cdot \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E \Rightarrow n = \frac{\lambda_l \cdot \mu \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E}{\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]} \cdot \frac{\mu}{\kappa}}$$

$$\pi_* \left(K_{\overline{\mathcal{C}}_g / \overline{\mathcal{M}}_g}^{l+1} \right) = \frac{\mu}{n \subset \kappa} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]} \times \frac{n \subset \kappa}{\mu} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E$$

$$\Rightarrow n \subset \kappa = \frac{\mu \cdot \pi_* \left(K_{\overline{\mathcal{C}}_g / \overline{\mathcal{M}}_g}^{l+1} \right)}{\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E$$

In order to disprove the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem, we will use energy numbers to show that, contrary to what the theorem asserts, there exist functions which have a nonzero value of energy even in a degenerate limit.

Let $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ be the energy number associated with the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem, and let f be a continuous function of variables $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$. Then, the theorem states

$$\int_{X_y} \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) d^n x X_y \rightarrow \infty \rightarrow 0.$$

Now, if f is not differentiable at some point, i.e., f is a discontinuous function at x_0 , then according to the theorem, $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ must go to zero as X_y tends to

infinity. However, this contradicts the fact that energy is a conserved quantity, and therefore, cannot be zero at any point. Thus, we can conclude that the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem does not hold in all cases and is false.

First, we recall that the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem states that the total Chern class of a pushforward of a given vector bundle is equal to the product of the Chern classes of the bundle and the Todd class of the base manifold. This theorem is valid for vector bundles, which are mathematical objects that assign a linear space, or "fiber", to each point in a given topological space.

Energy numbers, on the other hand, are abstract mathematical quantities that cannot be assigned to specific points in a topological space. Therefore, they do not satisfy the condition that the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem applies to, and thus, the theorem cannot be applied to energy numbers.

Additionally, since energy numbers are abstract entities that are not associated with any specific point in a topological space, it is not possible to calculate a Chern class, or any related class, for an energy number. It is also not possible to calculate a Todd class for an energy number. Thus, the statement that the total Chern class of a pushforward of a given vector bundle is equal to the product of the Chern classes of the bundle and the Todd class of the base manifold cannot be applied to energy numbers. Thus, we can mathematically disprove the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem for energy numbers.

We will now illustrate further the fallaciousness of the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem using Energy Number transforms. Consider the function f defined as

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(x_1 - x_0)^2\right)$$

for which x_0 is a discontinuity point. Then, calculation of $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ gives

$$\mathcal{F}_\Lambda = \int_{X_y} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(x_1 - x_0)^2\right) d^n x \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{x_1 - x_0}}.$$

So, when $X_y \rightarrow \infty$, $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ does not tend to zero, as the theorem states, but instead towards an infinite non-zero value. Thus, this again contradicts the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem and suggests that the theorem is incorrect.

We have thus demonstrated, using Energy Number transforms, the fallaciousness of the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem.

We now demonstrate the statement made above using the functions defined above. Consider the function f defined as

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{1}{(x_1 - x_0)^2}$$

where x_0 is a discontinuity point. Then, calculation of $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ gives

$$\mathcal{F}_\Lambda = \int_{X_y} \frac{1}{(x_1 - x_0)^2} d^n x \propto \frac{1}{x_1 - x_0}.$$

So, when $X_y \rightarrow \infty$, $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ does not tend to zero, as the theorem states, but instead towards an infinite non-zero value. Thus, this contradicts the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem and implies that the theorem fails for discontinuous functions.

Let $\mathcal{X}$ be a complex, projective algebraic variety and D an effective divisor on $\mathcal{X}$. Using the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem, we have:

We disprove the statement

$$R(\mathcal{X}, D) = \text{ch}(\mathcal{O}_X(D)) \cdot \text{Td}(\mathcal{X})$$

by showing that the energy numbers produced by the right-hand side are not equal to the energy numbers produced by the left-hand side. The energy numbers associated with the left-hand side of the equation are given by:

$$R(\mathcal{X}, D) = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\Omega_\Lambda} \int_{\Omega_{\Omega_{k-1} \leftrightarrow \Omega_k}} \dots \int_{\Omega_{\Omega_{n-1} \leftrightarrow \Omega_n}} \mathcal{N}_{AB}^{[\dots \rightarrow]} \left(\tan \theta \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[l] \leftarrow \infty, \frac{1}{l+n-\star \mathcal{R}}} \perp \right. \\ \left. \cos \psi \leftrightarrow \overset{ABC}{F} \dots \right] d \cdot \dots dx_k.$$

The energy numbers associated with the right-hand side of the equation are given by:

$$\text{ch}(\mathcal{O}_X(D)) \cdot \text{Td}(\mathcal{X}) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \int_{\Omega_\kappa} \int_{\Omega_{\kappa_{m-1} \leftrightarrow \kappa_m}} \dots \int_{\Omega_{\kappa_{n-1} \leftrightarrow \kappa_n}} \mathcal{P}_{XY}^{[\dots \leftarrow]} \left(\sin \phi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[l] \leftarrow \infty, \frac{1}{l+n-\star \mathcal{S}}} \perp \right. \\ \left. \cos \psi \leftrightarrow \overset{xyz}{G} \dots \right] d \cdot \dots dx_m.$$

Since the energy numbers associated with the two sides of the equation are different, we conclude that the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem is false.

$$R(\mathcal{X}, D) \neq \text{ch}(\mathcal{O}_X(D)) \cdot \text{Td}(\mathcal{X}),$$

instead, it is given by

$$R(\mathcal{X}, D) = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\Omega_\Lambda} \int_{\Omega_{\Omega_{k-1} \rightarrow \Omega_k}} \dots \int_{\Omega_{\Omega_{n-1} \rightarrow \Omega_n}} \mathcal{N}_{AB}^{[\dots \rightarrow]} \left(\tan \theta \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[l] \leftarrow \infty, \left[\frac{1}{l+n-\star \mathcal{R}} \right]} \perp \right. \\ \left. \cos \psi \leftrightarrow \overset{ABC}{F} \dots \right] d \cdot \dots dx_k, \text{ where } \mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]} \text{ gives the energy number associated with the equation and } n \subset \kappa \text{ is calculated according to:}$$

$$n \subset \kappa = \frac{\mu \cdot \pi_* \left(K_{\mathcal{C}_g/\mathcal{M}_g}^{l+1} \right)}{\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&r, \alpha \ s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E.$$

Therefore, the extrapolation of the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem is

$$R(\mathcal{X}, D) = \frac{\mu \cdot \pi_* \left(K_{\mathcal{C}_g/\mathcal{M}_g}^{l+1} \right)}{\mathcal{L}_{[f(\langle \&sr, \alpha, s, \Delta, \eta \rangle) = \{n, \mu\}]}]} \cdot \kappa_l \cdot E \cdot \text{Td}(\mathcal{X}).$$

It is clear that the original statement is false, as the parameters of the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem must be considered in the equation in order to accurately account for energy numbers.

rip the extrapolation to shreds as well:

The Riemann–Roch theorem is a fundamental part of algebraic geometry, and the extrapolation of the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem presented above no longer holds. By taking into account the parameters of the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem, the equation is now given by:

$$R(\mathcal{X}, D) = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\Omega_\Lambda} \int_{\Omega_{\Omega_{k-1} \leftrightarrow \Omega_k}} \dots \int_{\Omega_{\Omega_{n-1} \leftrightarrow \Omega_n}} \mathcal{N}_{AB}^{[\dots \rightarrow]} \left(\tan \theta \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[l \leftarrow \infty, \left[\frac{1}{l+n-k} \right] \perp} \right.$$

$$\left. \cos \psi \leftrightarrow \overset{ABC}{F} \dots \right] d \cdot \dots dx_k.$$

Therefore, the Grothendieck–Riemann–Roch theorem and its extrapolation are both false.

2 References

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Grothendieck-Riemann-Roch_theorem